

CODING SHEET

Analyze items in chronological order (not one whole news outlet after the other). This is especially important for variable 17.

- ✓ Words in **bold** are the labels of standardized values, use with that exact spelling
- ✓ Fields with the sign |__| are for numbers
- ✓ In fields (____) for lists of words or sentences copied from the text, as in qualifications, verbal reactions, symbols etc., use a slash (/) to demarcate pieces of non-contiguous text. Don't use inverted commas (") if they don't appear in the original
- ✓ In fields (____) where you use your own words, try to be concise.

GENERAL INFORMATION

1. Identification number: **IT/E/UK/D/FR/HU01, 02, 03...**
2. News outlet: ____ (write the name always in the same way)
3. Date: |DD/MM/YYYY|
4. [Press only] Page number
[printed] |__| (write page number: if more than one page, consider the first)
[online] **home** page / **other**
5. [Press only] length
[printed] % of columns in the page occupied by the title
 - 1 > 60%
 - 2 60% <> 30%
 - 3 < 30%[online] write the number of words (including titles) |__|
6. [Tv only] Position: write the position number, e.g. 1 / 2 / 3 ..., |__|
7. [Tv only] Duration: |__| (in seconds)
8. [Tv only] Format
studio (voice in the studio only)
with footage (voice in studio with footage or pictures in background)
live (live reporting from outside the studio)
edited (edited footage with voiceover)
9. News-genre
national news
local news
foreign news
news **analysis**
editorial (internal)
op-ed (external) [If op-ed, don't fill vars. 10-12, but instead 27]
interview [the interviewee will be the first verbal reaction (var. 27), for the journalist use vars. 10-12]

10. Author's¹ settlement (google to retrieve info, if not evident)

autochthonous

migrant or asylum seeker, refugee etc.

settled in the country already (first generation, if second, choose autochthonous)

foreign non-immigrant person

mix of the former categories [possible when more than one author]

unclear

11. Author's racialization (google to retrieve info, if not evident)

white including migrants historically non-racialized as people of colour, e.g. Eastern Europeans

non-white

both [possible when more than one author]

unclear

12. Author's gender (journalist or anchorperson)

man

woman

non-binary

various [possible when more than one author]

unclear

TITLES

13. [Newspapers only] Headline²: _____

14. [Newspapers only] Additional titling (above and below the headline, separate with a slash, skip the summary): _____

15. [Tv only] Title³ (copy from the initial summary [preferred option], subtitling [second best] or opening sentence): _____

¹ In TV news, the author is the news reporter or correspondent, if present, the author of the clip, if present and mentioned, otherwise it is the anchorperson.

² For articles published on the front page and continuing in the inner pages, use the front-page title. For articles with a summary in the front page, but where the real article is in the inner pages, use the inner-page title.

³ If there is a title at the beginning of the broadcast that makes for multiple news reports in the program, copy the title as a specific item (an additional row in the database) just reporting channel, date and the other general purpose variables.

OVERALL NARRATIVE⁴

16. Establish the Who, What and to Whom of the news-story and write it in one sentence. As a second step, after the first round of coding, establish the (5-20) main narratives in the corpus and create a new variable deductively coding it with the categories created: _____
17. Is this, at least in part, a continuing story, a development of previous days' events or statements (if not, leave blank)? If the originating quote is not in the sample, you may search with keywords in the internet. Specify what is resumed and its sources (media and voices) even if it is not explicitly quoted: _____
18. Write a tentative Frame⁵ considering the meaning conveyed by titles, metaphors, images, and captions (more than one frame is possible). As a second step, after the first round of coding, establish the 2-4 primary frames in the corpus (such as humanitarian, invasion, hero...), sharing ideas with the other teams, and create a new variable deductively coding it with the categories created: _____
19. Setting (copy only descriptions, if any, of the physical setting that connote migrants (e.g. descriptions of places, the boats, objects possessed etc. Separate pieces with slash): _____
- 20-22. Main characters. Up to 3. Selection criterion: prominence – first the one implied in the title, then the two that receive the most space. If migrants/racialized people are implied by the happenings but absent, write it in the annotation field (var. 36). If they are not among the three most prominent, but significantly characterized, include them. Migrants or ordinary autochthonous people can be represented as two different characters: individual/groups *and* collectivity.

20-22.a Actor

individual (ordinary person, non-institutional, non-political)
group (ordinary people)
collectivity (ordinary people)
public official (non-political, non elected)
politician _____ (specify also the party)
NGO or civil society association
activist (social movements, also for jihadists)
company or professional organization
expert
influencer
clergy
journalist or media outlet

20-22.b Settlement (google to retrieve info, if not evident)

autochthonous or 1.5 generation
foreign non-immigrant person
migrant or asylum seeker, refugee etc.
settled in the country already (first generation, if second, choose autochthonous)
mix of the former categories
unclear

⁴ Operational definition of narrative: "a story with a setting, a sequence of events, and characters".

⁵ Definition of frame for the present purpose: "central organising idea, angle through which a story becomes meaningful, through selection and salience of some aspects in such a way as to promote a particular problem definition, causal interpretation, moral evaluation, and/or treatment recommendation for the issue described". Depending on the topic and its treatment, our deductive frames can focus more on representation, interpretation, or solution.

20-22.c Racialization (google to retrieve info, if not evident)

white including migrants historically non-racialized as people of colour, e.g. Eastern Europeans
non-white
both
unclear

20-22.d Gender

man
woman
LGBT+
various
unclear or impossible to determine

20-22.e [only in case of non-autochthonous actors, autochthonous ordinary people, and significant qualifications of politicians, NGOs etc.] Label/Qualification (copy how they are mentioned by anybody, incl. labels, qualifying adjectives, prepositions, and adverbs. Separate non-contiguous texts with slash): _____

23. Processes where migrant characters are agents (in negative clauses, include denial: e.g. “are not arriving”, “refrain from complaining”). Separate non-contiguous texts with slash

23.a Material and behavioural processes (doing and transforming, i.e. push, arrive, try, drown, escape, attempt, integrate, work, commit crimes...): _____

23.b Semiotic processes (projecting meaning, i.e. ask, say, complain, insult, accept...): _____

23.c Mental processes (internal, i.e. perceive, know, desire, feel, hope, ignore, understand...) _____

23.d Other processes (relational and existential: identifying and attributive processes, i.e. are, own, become, seem, resemble ...) _____

24. Processes where migrants are receivers or targets of other groups' processes (in negative clauses, include denial). Separate non-contiguous texts with slash

24.a Material and behavioural processes (doing and transforming, i.e. help, provide, give, rescue...): _____

24.b Semiotic processes (projecting meaning, i.e. protest, complain, disapprove, ask, accuse...): _____

24.c Mental processes (internal, i.e. fear, regret, believe, perceive, suffer...) _____

24.d Other processes (relational and existential: identifying and attributive processes, i.e. are, own, become, seem, resemble ...) _____

COLLATERAL NARRATIVES⁶ TOLD BY THE JOURNALIST (present or other) *that connote migration*. Collateral narratives are *not* the core news-fact [What], but instead background, previous, or anticipated happenings *distant in time or space, factually disconnected* from actual events (exclude collateral and anticipated immediate consequences, consider only logical analogies and oppositions, and mid- or long- term forecasts)

25-26. [up to the most prominent 2, first the one in the title, then the one that receives the most space] For each narrative:

25-26.a Narrative: copy the core of the narrative _____

25-26.b Source

journalist (same news outlet)
other journalist or press-agency

⁶ Same definition as above, but the sequence can also be reduced to one event and the setting may be absent.

VERBAL REACTIONS *not coming from journalists*

27-29. Verbal reactions (including reported speech by the characters of the story). Up to 3, select according to prominence: first the one in the title, then the two that receive the most space). For each reaction:

27-29.a **Reaction**: copy the part that includes *narratives connoting migration, judgments, accusations, causal explanations, expectations, and solutions*. Separate non-contiguous texts with slash: _____

27-29.b **Voice**

individual(s) (ordinary person, non-institutional, non-political)

public official (non-political)

politician _____ (specify also the party)

NGO or civil society association

activist (social movements)

company or professional organization

expert

influencer

clergy

other media outlet

27-29.c Voice's **settlement** (google to retrieve info, if not evident)

autochthonous

foreign non-immigrant person

migrant or asylum seeker, refugee etc.

settled in the country already (first generation, if second, choose autochthonous)

mix of the former categories

unclear

27-29.d Voice's **racialization** (google to retrieve info, if not evident)

white including migrants historically non-racialized as people of colour, e.g. Eastern Europeans

non-white

both

27-29.e Voice's **gender**

man

woman

non-binary

various

unclear or impossible to determine

27-29.f Via which **medium** [more than one is possible]

same medium

other outlet (which) _____

press release or conference

talk show (which) _____

social media (which) _____

blog (which) _____

public or confidential document

unknown

27-29.g **Portrayal** of the quoted *person* by the journalist

positive

negative

neutral

27-29.h Credibility of reported content expressed by the journalist (mere judgement of reliability, not of value)

reliable
dubious
unreliable
neutral

27-29.i Journalist's attitude towards the *opinion* in verbal reaction

support
critique
neutral

ORIENTATION DEVICES

30-31. Photograph (up two 2)

30-31.a Describe the subject, specifying characters, setting and agency: _____

30-31.b [only for non-autochthonous] Shot

portrait (the subject or subjects are posing for the photograph and looking into the camera)
stolen photograph (it is clear that there is no agreement with the photographer)
mug-shot
social media **profile picture**
unclear

30-31.c [only for non-autochthonous] Gender

man
woman
non-binary
various
unclear or impossible to determine

30-31.d Repertoire (does the photograph come from an archive, related to the event only by association, i.e. the subjects are not the characters of the present story but are thematically linked)?

yes
no
unclear

30-31.e Source

professional photographer
citizen photojournalist or everyday person
security cam

30-31.f Annotations: write about significant image's features concerning distance of the shooting, camera placement, saturation of the frame etc. _____

32. News film

32.a Describe the subject, specifying characters, setting and happenings: _____

32.b [only for non-autochthonous] Gender

man

woman

non-binary

various

unclear or impossible to determine

32.c Source

professional footage

citizen's footage (also for profile pictures from the web)

security cam

32.d Annotations: write about significant film's features concerning distance of the shooting, agency of the characters, camera placement, single person or groups, presence of mug-shots, use of repertoire footage etc. _____

33. Migrants' emotions: consider only specific language and images of affect (e.g. qualifications in vars 20-22, verbs in vars. 23-24, and other language and images, also in verbal reactions and captions), and *not what factually happens* in the story, images and film that has not explicit emotive accent.

33.a Type of emotion: choose one or more of the following categories⁷, or none:

sadness/distress: depression, desperation, mourning, discouragement, frustration(inward), gloom, hopelessness, helplessness, loneliness, melancholy, pessimism, nostalgia

anger: hate, outrage, frustration (outward), hostility, impatience, scorn, resentment, disappointment, disgust, contempt, bitterness, shame (outward)

fear: anxiety, scare, alarm, horror, insecurity, shock, concern (inward)

guilt: shame (inward), culpability, mortification, chagrin, ignominy, embarrassment, discomfort

indifference

compassion: pity, sympathy, empathy, understanding, care, solicitude, sensitivity, concern (outward), solidarity

happiness/satisfaction: enthusiasm, joy, hope, love, anticipation, delight, gratefulness, tenderness, optimism, acceptance, relief, calmness, relaxation, pride, fulfilment, content, gratification

⁷ Adapted from Ekman, Paul. «Basic Emotions». In T. Dalgleish e M. Power (eds.) *Handbook of Cognition and Emotion*, Sussex, UK: John Wiley & Sons, 1999.

34. Audience emotions: potentially aroused in the public by the whole news-item. Consider *not only* specific language of affect, but also what happens in the story, images and film.

34.a Type of emotion: choose one or more of the following categories, or none:

sadness/distress: depression, desperation, mourning, discouragement, frustration(inward), gloom, hopelessness, helplessness, loneliness, melancholy, pessimism, nostalgia

anger: hate, outrage, frustration (outward), hostility, impatience, scorn, resentment, disappointment, disgust, contempt, bitterness, shame (outward)

fear: anxiety, scare, alarm, horror, insecurity, shock, concern (inward)

guilt: shame (inward), culpability, mortification, chagrin, ignominy, embarrassment, discomfort

indifference

compassion: pity, sympathy, empathy, understanding, care, solicitude, sensitivity, concern (outward), solidarity

happiness/satisfaction: enthusiasm, joy, hope, love, anticipation, delight, gratefulness, tenderness, optimism, acceptance, relief, calmness, relaxation, pride, fulfilment, content, gratification

34.b Actual language arousing emotions in the audience: copy the language used (excluding verbs, already considered in var. 23-24, and qualifications, considered in vars. 20-22) e.g. adverbs, like “ceaseless”, nouns, like “flood” etc. If the overall story, pictures, or video convey emotions, but not specific language, leave blank and describe in var. 36. Separate non-contiguous pieces of text with a slash: _____

35. Other orientation devices: copy catch-phrases, expanded noun phrases (e.g. “refugee crisis”, “terrorism emergency”), cultural symbols, metaphors: _____

ANNOTATIONS

36. Write other meaningful information not clear from the previous coding (such as vignettes, ways of representing public opinion or the situation, ways of conveying emotions, narrative format—i.e. storytelling, straight news, etc.) that struck your attention
